

Search & Rescue With Quadruped Robots: What Rescuers Need and What Roboticians can Do

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Abstract—This paper proposes the results of an interview with members of ANPAS (National Association of Public Assistance) to understand what are the procedures to be completed in a Search and Rescue scenario. The interview focused on the possible use of autonomous quadruped robots during disaster management. It is also presented an exploration strategy specific to autonomous robots in search and rescue scenarios. The exploration strategy is based on the need for fast information gathering and time constraints to ensure safety for people inside the building and also for rescuers that have to enter the building.

Index Terms—Search & Rescue, quadruped robots, exploration

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural disasters are rapidly increasing in the past 50 years; in 1970 there were a total of 76 natural disasters while in 2022 there were 423 episodes [1]. Due to this, many countries have started to increase the number of policies to prepare for natural disasters, which has caused a significant reduction in deaths. The main areas of research to reduce the effects of natural disasters on the population are the prediction of disasters, the construction of resilient infrastructures, the preparation of the population for possible emergencies, and the response system. In the past years, several robotic applications have been developed to improve disaster management, especially for what concerns the prediction and response system.

Robots used during disaster management can help increase the safety of rescuers by reaching areas that are not safe. In the work of Delmerico et al. [2], it is presented that one of the main tasks of autonomous robots for search and rescue is providing sensing abilities to rescuers that are in safe areas.

Our work focuses on the development of a system architecture, based on the needs of rescuers, that allows robots to work autonomously together with rescuers to collect information and sensor data in a post-natural disaster scenario.

In general, it takes some time for rescuers to reach the buildings that have been affected. Autonomous robots can start operations without the need for someone to be on the scene controlling them. The robot collects data about the

environment safely and can then provide them to rescuers whenever they arrive.

To implement an autonomous robot able to start the operations of search and rescue in this paper we present a two-fold contribution that is explained in the following section:

- Understand the needs of rescuers: based on an interview with first responders what are the most important phases of rescues and what points should be improved;
- Implement an exploration strategy that will be the base of the entire architecture.

II. METHODOLOGY

To gather information about the current procedures adopted by first responders in Italy we gathered members of ANPAS (National Association of Public Assistance) and the Civil Protection and we discussed their procedures and their opinions on how those can be improved by deploying a quadruped robot, such as Spot from Boston Dynamics. Thinking especially of earthquakes the series of operations to be completed is: (i) checking the safety of the scene, (ii) detecting people in the environment, (iii) finding a safe path to reach people, (iv) checking consciousness, (v) checking other health parameters.

For the first task, rescuers suggested creating a map of the environment that records the presence of obstacles, such as parts of plaster and collapsed ceilings. They also mentioned the importance of gas sensors to check for the presence of harmful gasses, explosives, and also the percentage of oxygen.

While detecting people rescuers mentioned the need to mount sensors able to recognize the human shape even if hidden, people might be scared or might be injured behind debris; using vision-based strategies only is not optimal and prone to errors. To generate a safe path a first approach to the problem could be saving the trajectory of the robot.

Finally, the most important health parameters are the temperature of the person, which can be retrieved using a thermal camera, and the level of consciousness of the person. For this last part, rescuers mentioned three different levels of response: to call, to touch, and to pain; the robot can easily test the response to call using speakers and a microphone, for the other two levels it is more difficult to use the robot but, for example, if the robot has an external arm mounted, it can be used to touch the person and assess response to touch.

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It is important to mention that all of them imagined the operations of the robot to continue autonomously even after people reach the scene. They do not think it is feasible to train all of the operators and to keep all of them trained to use the robot after a disaster. Another aspect to take into consideration is that whenever rescuers encounter people inside the building they must complete a series of operations that slow down the operation, if the robot continues the exploration autonomously then it keeps collecting information.

From the results of the interview, it is possible to conclude that the architecture of the robot should be based on an exploration strategy that allows the robot to move between floors. On top of the exploration strategy, different policies can be applied to gather the needed data.

The exploration strategy we developed is based on the work of Umari et al. [3]. It is a frontier-based strategy that detects frontiers both in the proximity of the robot and in more remote areas of the map based on the construction of two rapidly exploring random trees. The frontiers are then evaluated based on both the quality of the frontier and the cost of the motion. The parameters that influence the choice of the next frontier to visit, each multiplied by a weight are:

- the expected information gain. It is the amount of squared meters of unexplored space in a circular area around the frontier;
- the Euclidean distance to the frontier. It represents the cost of reaching the given frontier;
- the floor gain. It is the area that is yet to be explored on the current floor of the robot or the floor the robot will reach by climbing the stairs. It is calculated as the difference between the max area of each floor and the current area explored on the floor;
- the orientation gain. It is an optimization gain that allows the robot to prefer frontiers that are in the motion direction of the robot;
- the curve cost. It is a cost that allows the robot to prefer frontiers that are reachable with a mostly straight path, it is calculated as the ratio between the path calculated using a Dijkstra algorithm and the Euclidean distance;

The floor gain, the orientation gain, and the curve cost have been implemented to obtain a behaviour that allows the robot to move in the environment discovering as much space as possible. Since the task is time constrained the robot should explore areas that guarantee a lot of new information to be gathered; the robot should not waste time exploring small corners of space. Assuming that the robot will be deployed in public buildings, another desirable behaviour is the exploration of first the hallways and then the rooms that open around such hallways, for this reason, in the first phases of the exploration, it is better to prefer frontiers that are in front of the robot, along the hallways rather than entering rooms.

We tested our exploration strategy at the university building by repeating the experiment with different values of the weights. In Fig. 1 the area that was mapped after 10 minutes of autonomous exploration. From the results, it is possible to see that the worst-performing trial was the one where the robot

had the floor gain set to zero, it would explore completely each floor before climbing the stairs to reach the next one. The performance also decreases when the floor gain is too high due to the time it takes the robot to change the floor, the robot would waste time climbing stairs as soon as some small area was discovered.

Fig. 1. Squared Meters explored changing the Floor Gain of the exploration.

III. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose the results of an interview with members of ANPAS and Civil Protection to understand what they would need from robots in the aftermath of a natural disaster. The most significant aspect that emerged is the need for a robot that autonomously explores the building even if rescuers are present on the scene. Based on the results of the interview we developed an exploration strategy that could be the base of the autonomous operations of the robot. The robot explores the entire building while collecting data from different sensors in the building and reporting those data to operators that can plan their future actions accordingly.

This is just the first approach to the problem, the exploration should be tested in more unstructured environments to be considered efficient. There is also the need to implement strategies to recognize the location of people and mark them on the map and integrate the other sensors that have been mentioned

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